

ISic1082

I.Sicily inscription 1082

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.11.10 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-12-21 - Jonathan Prag minor edits

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

localita S. Nicola

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory C311

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Πολυστεφάνω
2. Σωτείρα
3. Νικομήδης ὁ καὶ
4. Ὄνυς ΣωτίραΣωτείρα

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492710

EDR 136140

EDCS 70900050

EDCS 39102239

PHI 140564

PHI 331328

Bibliography

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